

Systematic review and meta-analysis

Toward soil health assessment in a life cycle perspective: Linking soil stressors to damage to ecosystem services

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ABSTRACT

Healthy soils are essential for life on Earth and a prerequisite for maintaining various important ecosystem services. As a result, management recommendations to improve soil health are increasingly being incorporated into legislation. Several frameworks for evaluating soil health have been proposed in the past three decades. However, our understanding of how soil biodiversity loss translates into damage to relevant soil functions and related ecosystem services remains scattered. To address this gap, we evaluated the scientific literature to map how different terrestrial organisms contribute to specific soil processes and functions, and ultimately how the loss of functional diversity leads to damage across 12 distinct soil-related ecosystem services. Drawing inspiration from life cycle impact assessment, we propose a full damage pathway that connects soil stressors (such as greenhouse gas emissions or land use) via fate, exposure and effect mechanisms on soil ecosystems, to the loss of soil functions and the services provided by soil. This is a first step toward the development of a systematic soil health assessment approach that considers the loss of soil functions and services as areas of protection, in alignment with life cycle assessment methods.

1. Introduction

Healthy soils, defined as those which can sustain a living ecosystem (Doran and Zeiss 2000; Guerra et al., 2020), host nearly 60% of Earth's biodiversity and produce over 98% of the food we consume (Kopittke et al., 2021; Anthony et al., 2023). Soil organisms partake in important ecological processes, the basis for soil functions and ecosystem services (Jónsson and Davíðsdóttir, 2016; Lehman et al., 2020), making soil health vital for overall human and planetary health (Wall et al., 2015; Stockdale et al., 2019; Guerra et al. 2020; Marselle et al., 2021; Kopittke et al., 2024). Well-functioning soils regulate critical Earth-system processes and planetary boundaries, via biogeochemical nutrient flows, climate regulation and water cycling (Ryberg et al., 2016; Bjørn et al., 2019; Kopittke et al., 2021).

Soil health has been defined as “the capability of a soil to maintain its functions for the support of life on Earth, including human lives” (see Glossary in Table 1). Soil health can be damaged via anthropogenic disturbances such as the release of contaminants (Dragović and Vulević,

2020; Lehmann et al., 2020), as well as greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and resulting temperature changes (Allen et al., 2011; Patil and Lamnganbi, 2018). Land use, such as soil sealing, can undermine all soil-related ecosystem services (Tobias et al., 2018; Tóth et al., 2022).

Soil formation can take up to several thousands of years (Duchaufour, 2012), with just a few years of malpractice rendering soil unsuitable for life support, making soil a non-renewable resource (Assennato et al., 2020; Fullen and Catt, 2014; Hatfield, 2014). The Food and Agriculture Organization estimates that 90% of the world's topsoil will be at risk of degradation by 2050, jeopardising food provision and human wellbeing (Kopittke et al., 2019; Hossain et al., 2020). This decline in soil quality reduces soils functionality, making soils more vulnerable to future stressors (Zhou et al., 2024). Hence, the preservation and regeneration of soils have become important sustainability goals (Lal et al., 2021; Veerman, 2023).

In the past decades, we have gained understanding of the mechanisms linking stressors, such as pollutant release and land use, to soil biodiversity loss. They form the basis for modelling impact metrics that

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Table 1
Terms and definitions relevant to soil health.

Term	Definition
Areas of protection	Categories of concern for safeguarding in impact assessment methodology (Hauschild and Huijbregts 2015; ISO, 2016).
Biodiversity	Measure of the distinctive biological units of a given ecosystem, including number of species and their molecular, phenotypical, ethological, and functional variability (United Nations, 1992).
Disturbance	Unpredictable event which modifies the structure and/or functioning of an ecosystem (Battisti et al., 2016).
Ecosystem goods	Quantifiable products of ecosystem services (de Groot et al., 2002, 2012). Example: kg of agricultural yield.
Functional diversity	Groups of organisms with shared traits that contribute to a given ecological process (Mammola et al., 2021).
Functional group	Set of organisms categorized according to their contributions to an ecological process (Cummins, 1974; Briones, 2014).
Insurance hypothesis	The more species within a role, the higher probability that some will be able to survive disturbance, maintaining and/or recovering ecosystem multifunctionality (Valone and Barber, 2008).
Impact category	Environmental issues of concern in Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA, see details below) which are aggregated based on their potential to damage areas of protection (Hauschild and Huijbregts, 2015; Rosenbaum et al., 2018).
Life cycle assessment (LCA)	Standardized framework to assess the impacts of a product or activity (Rebitzer et al., 2004; ISO, 2016; Bjørn et al., 2018).
Life cycle impact assessment (LCIA)	Expanded LCA including calculation of environmental impacts across different damage categories (Hauschild and Huijbregts 2015; ISO, 2016; Rosenbaum et al., 2018).
Multivariate ordination	Mathematical arrangement of multidimensional data into a bidimensional space to facilitate their clustering and ordination upon visual inspection (Chahouki, 2011).
Scoring curves	Mathematical relationship between a soil health indicator and the resulting soil function. There are three main types: more is better, less is better, and mid-optimum (Karlen and Stott, 1994).
Soil	Three-dimensional matrix where the lithosphere, hydrosphere, atmosphere and biosphere interact to create the upper layer of a planet crust (Van Es, 2017). On Earth, these interactions create a living ecosystem in which the mineral component contains at least some living organisms, organic matter, water and/or atmospheric gases (Doran, 2002).
Soil contamination	Presence of unwanted substances in soil above natural levels (Chapman, 2007). Here we refer to contaminants from anthropogenic sources (Lombi et al., 1998).
Soil degradation	The loss or reduction of soil functionality, whether naturally occurring or man-made (Blum, 2020).
Soil ecosystem services	Human benefits obtained from soil functions (Barbier et al., 2015). Services have a human-centric approach and refer to the value that humans derive from underlying ecosystem functions (de Groot et al., 2002, 2012).
Soil health	The capability of a soil to maintain its functions for the support of life on Earth, including human lives (Karlen et al., 2019).
Soil multifunctionality	The different functions and services occurring as a result of the interactions between the abiotic and biological components of soils (Creamer et al., 2022).
Soil microfunctions	Smallest units in which soil functions can be subdivided (Johnson, 1971; Xu et al., 2018).
Soil organisms	Soil inhabiting life forms, including those life cycle stages and parts which are restricted to the soil habitat (Blume et al., 2016).
Soil pollution	Contamination (see above) which results in damage to the physical and/or living environment (Chapman, 2007).
Soil processes	Biotic and abiotic soil activities which contribute to the formation and maintenance of the soil ecosystem (de Groot et al., 2002).
Soil resilience	The ability of a soil ecosystem to bounce back and recover its functionality to its initial state after removal of the disturbance (Seybold et al., 1999; Dodd et al., 2023).
Soil resistance	The ability of a soil ecosystem to resist alteration after a disturbance without noticeable change on its functionality (Seybold et al., 1999; Dodd et al., 2023).
Soil subfunctions	Smaller units encompassing several soil processes responsible for the delivery of specific ecosystem services (Greiner et al., 2017; Creamer et al., 2022).
Species diversity	Diversity measure which considers the phylogenetic distance between species (Ricotta 2004).
Species redundancy	Coexistence of several species with the same functional role for a given ecosystem (Setälä et al. 2005).

are used in environmental assessment of products or systems, such as life cycle assessment (LCA), allowing the translation of emissions or land use into potential impact on ecosystems. Existing life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) frameworks allow us to model fate, exposure and effects of environmental emissions (e.g., Soriano, 2014; Fantke et al., 2021; Peña et al., 2022; Owsianiak et al., 2023; Lebrun et al., 2025), characterizing their persistence, bioavailability and ecosystem damage (e.g. Khan et al., 2015; Hu et al., 2020; Oginah et al., 2025). However, their main limitation is a missing link between soil biodiversity loss and the understanding of soil health in terms of soil functions and related ecosystem services (e.g. Souza et al., 2015; Delgado-Baquerizo et al., 2025). By contrast, several soil health assessment frameworks have been developed, and it is of interest to examine what LCIA can potentially learn from them.

The aim of this conceptual review is therefore to examine key impact mechanisms in order to propose a full damage pathway, from GHG emissions, pollutants release and land use, to impacts on species biodiversity and the resulting damage to soil functions and services, with a focus on agricultural soils. This paper is organized as follows: (i) we summarize relevant soil health assessment frameworks; (ii) we provide an overview of the current understanding of damage mechanisms from emissions and other stressors to species biodiversity loss; (iii) we review soil functions, ecosystem services, and key taxa responsible for these, and propose a damage pathway connecting biodiversity loss with damage to soil functions and ecosystem services; and (iv) we discuss what is needed to operationalize this soil health assessment damage pathway in life cycle assessment.

2. Methods

2.1. Review of existing soil health assessment frameworks

Full details of the review procedure, including the exclusion process, are presented in Supplementary Information (SI, Sections S1.1 and S1.2). Identification of current soil health assessment methods was carried out using a systematic literature review. These were included in our review if the following criteria were met: (1) they allow for quantification of soil health scores; (2) they are developed specifically for soils (i.e., excluding estuarine and coastal ecosystems) (3) they are generic, meaning that they are applicable to various soil types (see details in SI, Section S2).

For the literature screening process, Boolean search strings were used in the “topic” section (i.e., title + abstract + keywords) of the Web of Science (WoS) Core Collection, and Google Scholar databases: “soil” OR “soil quality” OR “soil condition” AND “health” OR “functionality” AND “assessment” OR “evaluation” OR “monitoring” AND “framework” OR “method” OR “approach” OR “technique”. We also looked up the Scopus and PubMed databases, but these did not yield any relevant results. The time window for our search terms was from 01/01/1990 to 30/08/2024 (pre-prints included).

Similarly, identification of soil functions, ecosystem services, and relevant soil organisms was also carried out via systematic literature review. A combination of the keywords “soil” AND “function*” AND “service*” in the topic sections of WoS and Google Scholar databases (time window: 01/01/1990 to 30/08/2024, pre-prints included).

2.2. Linking stressors to species diversity

The following categories of soils stressors were included in the present study: (1) climate forcers such as greenhouse gas emissions; (2) releases of organic and metallic compounds, (3) plastic emissions; and (4) releases of nutrients and acidifying substances. Their inclusion was based on recognized contribution to the loss of terrestrial species biodiversity (e.g., Phillips et al., 2024). We also included (5) land use, which represents a resource flow rather than an emission, as it is an important driver of terrestrial species biodiversity loss via habitat change mechanisms (Smith et al., 2016). The identification of these dominant impact mechanisms, from emission or land use up to the loss of species biodiversity was done based on scientific publications published in the past decade in the area of life cycle impact assessment, following established global guidelines (e.g., Bulle et al., 2019; Inaba and Itsubo, 2018;) and methodologies (e.g., Verones et al., 2022; Frischknecht et al., 2018). As starting point for the review, we consulted chapters of the Global Guidance on Life Cycle Impact Assessment Indicators which provided a systematic analysis of life cycle impact assessment methods and recommended practice in impact modelling (Bulle et al., 2019; Frischknecht et al., 2016; Frischknecht et al., 2018).

2.3. Linking species biodiversity to soil functionality loss

Recognizing the importance of soil functions in fulfilling ecosystem services, we propose focusing on functional diversity (see Glossary in Table 1), examining species loss and its consequences for soil-related ecosystem services. The focus on soil (sub)functions and ecological processes enables the connection between specific traits within soil communities (Ferris and Tuomisto, 2015; Eisenhauer et al., 2019), as well as the resulting ecosystem services (Creamer et al., 2022; Vazquez et al., 2025). Overall, we: (1) list key groups of organisms responsible for carrying out specific soil functions, (2) identify relevant soil functions and ecosystem services; and (3) match each function or subfunction to its main resulting ecosystem service(s). This was done via systematic literature reviews. The full list of selected studies and identified functions and services can be found in the SI, Section S3. The main steps are presented below.

2.3.1. Matching soil organisms to functions

To facilitate linking the loss of soil functionality to damage to ecosystem services, we included ecosystem services if a clear link between one or more soil function(s) and the ecosystem service of interest was established. We retained links between soil functions and ecosystem services as specified in the reviewed literature. If the link between soil functions and service was not specified in the reviewed study, we linked function to service using the works of Creamer et al. (2022) and Evangelista et al. (2023) outlining links between discrete soil processes to functions, subfunctions and services. This resulted in a total of 12 soil functions matched to each service (see Results for details).

We considered the role of plants, microbes, fungi and fauna in the soil system obtained from studies directly linking soil organisms to their associated processes and soil functions (e.g., Briones, 2014; Faucon et al., 2017; Creamer et al., 2022; Cao et al., 2023). Our classification of soil organisms was functional-based, resembling early attempts by Whittaker (1959 and 1969).

First, we classified soil organisms according to main kingdom: (1) plants (kingdom Plantae); (2) most protists and prokaryotes, i.e., microbes (old kingdom Protista, modern super kingdom Prokariota); (3) fungi (kingdom Fungi); and (4) fauna (mostly kingdom Animalia) (Whittaker, 1959, 1969; Margulis and Chapman, 2009; Hagen, 2012). To further facilitate the connection between functional diversity and the delivery of functions and services, intra kingdom divisions were based on functional groups (e.g., Briones, 2014; Potapov, 2022). Some unicellular eukaryotes were classified as microflora (phototrophic, chemotrophic) or “microfauna” (bacterivorous, predatory), as commonly

addressed by soil biology literature depending upon their trophic group and size class (Blume et al., 2015; Nadarajah, 2019).

Although plants are not strictly considered soil organisms, we have included them, owing to their direct influence on various soil processes (e.g., Baldi, 2021). They were subdivided according to their life forms and successional trajectories, as these are a good indicator of their role in soil development and carbon and nutrient cycles (see Poorter et al., 2023; Taylor et al., 2023). Bryophytes were considered as a separate functional group due to the important role of soil biological crusts in soil formation (Belnap, 1999; Seppelt et al., 2016; Seitz et al., 2017).

Microbes were grouped together and subdivided according to their main energy sources as phototrophs and chemotrophs (e.g. Jassim et al., 2023). Additionally, we included root symbionts and root growth promoting bacteria as an important functional group aiding biomass production (Hayat et al., 2010; Vacheron et al., 2013; Noceto et al., 2021). We also included pathogenic microorganisms, owing to their role on population regulation and potential as biological control agents (e.g., Hurst et al. 2025). Fungi were subdivided into saprophytic, mutualistic and pathogenic, based on their global functional diversity in soils (Tedersoo et al., 2014).

For soil fauna, we considered their overall role in soil formation via bioturbation, irrespective of functional group (Wilkinson et al., 2009). For their functional subclassification, we followed trophic diversity, as they mainly participate in different soil functions via resource reallocation (e.g., Briones, 2014; Creamer et al., 2022; Van Leeuwen et al., 2019). We also included pollinators as a soil fauna functional group to account for ground nesting pollinators and their essential role in biodiversity maintenance (e.g., Fantke et al., 2018; Christmann, 2022). Predatory and bacterial feeding unicellular eukaryotes like some protozoans were considered here as part of the soil microfauna (e.g. Blume et al., 2015; Nadarajah, 2019). While we draw inspiration from the work or Creamer et al. (2022), we suggest functional, rather than taxonomical, grouping of soil organisms as an approach to better underpin the different actors behind soil functions and the delivery of services.

2.3.2. Selected soil functions and links to ecosystem services

A list of selected ecological soil processes, (sub)functions and organisms can be found in Creamer et al. (2022). We expand on this list, to cover all soil functions and their related services (see Glossary in Table 1), including those independent from biodiversity (i.e., archive of information and platform for human activities). We identified potential soil functions, as originally reported by authors in the reviewed studies. We started from soil functions specified in systematic and comprehensive studies of Adhikari and Hartemink (2016), Bouma et al. (2017), Bünemann et al. (2018) and Lilburne et al. (2020). They were expanded to include population regulation and the resulting biological control of pests and diseases (e.g., Pulleman et al., 2012; Baveye et al., 2016; Greiner et al., 2017), owing to their benefits to human and agroecosystem health (Bünemann et al., 2018; Jaworski et al., 2023; Stavi et al., 2016).

We have also considered the provision of pharmaceutical and genetic resources, as a separate service enclosed within the molecular and genetic diversity of the soil inhabiting organisms (Van Leeuwen et al., 2019; Greiner et al., 2017; Thiele-Bruhn, 2021). However, we have not included the subfunctions of gas exchange and plant growth promotion, to avoid double counting, as they are already covered in our proposed pathway by the biogeochemical cycling of nutrients and the prevention of diseases, respectively (Mishra et al., 2017; Deng et al., 2022; Hartmann and Six, 2023). The concepts for soil functions, subfunctions and underlying processes were harmonized using the nomenclature proposed in Evangelista et al. (2023). Each main soil function was paired with their main resulting ecosystem service, to facilitate streamlining in a cause to effect chain, in accordance with impact assessment methods (Rugani et al., 2019; Taelman et al. 2024). In total, 12 ecosystem services were considered, which are discussed in detail in the following section.

Table 2

Current soil health assessment frameworks listed in chronological order, including their intended purpose, key indicators used and calculation of final soil health score.

Framework	Purpose	Key indicators	Score calculation
SQI (Doran and Parkin, 1994)	Assessment of soil quality and functionality across ecosystems and regions	Food and fibre production, erosivity, groundwater quality, surface water quality, air quality, food quality	Indicators are assigned weighting factors, final score calculated as a composite average
SMAF (Andrews, 1998)	Monitor soil loss, dynamic health, and land-use effects to soil health based on stakeholder preferences	13 physical, chemical and biological indicators	Principal component analysis (PCA) for indicator selection, standard scoring functions (SSF) for weighting and normalization into a single score
AEPAT (Liebig et al., 2004)	Monitor the long-term performance of agricultural practices	Indicators for agro-ecosystem functions	Contextual selection of relevant indicators for each soil function by end user, weighted and incorporated into a single indicator
SINDI (Lilburne et al., 2004)	Monitor soil physical, chemical and biological changes and their effects to local food production	Seven physio-chemical indicators	Indicators normalized and incorporated into a composite index
SCI (Zobeck et al., 2008)	Detect land management induced changes in topsoil soil organic matter (SOM)	Soil organic carbon dynamics	Single indicator
CASH (Idowu et al., 2009)	Monitor soil health changes to land use and cropping system	10 physical, chemical and biological indicators with optional add-ons (pathogens, salinity, metals...)	CASH specific algorithms are used to convert indicators into comparable scores weighted into a single indicator
ERICA (Boriani et al., 2010)	Assessment of pollution risks for human and ecological health	Ecotoxicological and human health parameters	Human and ecotoxicological effects are calculated for each pollutant, weighted, scored and combined to obtain the Substance Risk Index (SRI)
Haney's SHT (Haney et al., 2018)	Provide crop management recommendations	Water extractable organic C and N, extractable nitrate, ammonium, phosphate, Al, Fe, Ca, P and K; CO ₂ evolution	Metrics are expressed as ratios or ppm, then normalised and weighted into a single composite indicator
SQIP (Swanepoel et al., 2014)	Monitor land management practices (tillage, plant species, mulching and herbicide use) effects to pastures	Physical, chemical and biological indicators (e.g., bulk density, pH, exchangeable K, extractable P, β -glucosidase)	Separate principal component analysis (PCA) for each set of indicators, specific algorithms are used to convert indicators into comparable scores which are weighted into a single composite indicator
Alabama's method (Bosarge, 2015)	Differentiate long-term management induced changes (e.g., compaction, contamination)	10 chemical (e.g., pH, macro and micronutrients), one physical (aggregate stability) and one biological (soil respiration)	Indicator selection based on Auburn University soil testing laboratory guidelines, weighted score given as a percentage based on expert opinions
OSHA (Congreves et al., 2015)	Monitor the effects of tillage system and crop rotations in temperate agroecosystems	11 chemical (e.g., pH, cations), one physical (aggregate stability) and three biological (e.g., root health) indicators	Principal component analysis (PCA) for indicator selection, specific algorithms used to convert indicators into comparable scores, weighted into a single composite indicator
PGPE (Comin et al., 2016)	Assess erosion, compaction, nutrient depletion, salinization, organic matter (OM) loss and contamination/acidification of subtropical no tillage vegetable crop systems	Six soil quality indicators (total organic carbon, microbial biomass carbon, macroaggregate stability, bulk density, soil pH and available soil P)	Indicators locally selected according to study goals and expert opinions, scored in a scale of 1–10 or 1–5, and weighted to obtain a composite score
Farm-based soil health scorecard (Mann, 2017)	Monitor the effects of crop management to agricultural soil quality over time	Chemical, physical and biological measures, as well as plant and animal health indicators	Indicators selected based on farmers' interviews and given scores 1–5, matched with laboratory data, and summed to calculate overall soil health score
DRES (Ralisch et al., 2017)	Rapidly evaluate soil structural changes with land practices over time	Aggregate size and presence of biological structures	Indicator selection based on quick in situ evaluation of soil structure, 1–6 scores are given based on aggregate size and presence of biological structures (roots, earthworm casts, mycorrhizae...)
SQUID (Drobnik et al., 2018)	Monitor the effects of urbanization on agroecosystem performance	Several indicators used for each (sub) function assessed	Weighted score considering expert opinions (Delphi survey)
Meta-AHP (Xue et al., 2019)	Monitor land management effects on soil quality for different crops and farming systems	13 physical (e.g., water content), chemical (e.g., pH, organic matter, nutrients) and biological (e.g., respiration, microbial biomass) indicators	Indicators selected via meta-analysis, scores given based on analytical hierarchy processes and experts input. Indicators are weighted into a final composite score. Refinement of indicators and scores is done with long term field experiments
Soil Health Calculator (Jian et al., 2020)	Web-based tool to calculate soil health scores with minimal input	13 indicators: physical, chemical, biological, environmental and agronomic	Indicators selected via literature review and meta-analysis, scores given based on t-tests for indicator percentiles, hierarchical methods are used to assign groups of indicators to a colour scale (red to green), representing final Soil Health Score
SMI (Williams et al., 2020)	Monitor the effects of crop diversity and land management to soil health by farmers in Sweden	Crop diversity, years without disturbance and organic matter amendment	Aggregation of the three indicators into a single score
SHAPE (Nunes et al., 2021)	Measure the effects of land use and management practices among regional climate and soil conditions on a field scale	Soil organic carbon dynamics	Indicators selected via meta-analysis, scoring curves allocated via Bayesian model-based estimates. Scores given as a percentage, then aggregated into a single score
Multivariate Scoring Approach (Gyawali et al., 2022)	Used to assess the effects of different types of tillage and cover crops in agricultural soils.	33 biological, physical, chemical and plant growth (yield) parameters	Indicator relevance selected via a Bray Curtis permutational analysis of the variance (PERMANOVA)
Minimum Suite of Indicators (Bagnall et al., 2023)	Track the minimum amount of soil measurements needed to assess improvement resulting from management practices	37 soil properties	Indicator selection is qualitative following criteria of: relevant to soil health, responsive to management, applicable at scale and non-redundant
EUSO (Broothaerts et al., 2024)	Assessment of soil health in the context of the EU Soil Mission goals	19 chemical, physical and biological indicators	One indicator selected for each soil degradation process. Thresholds values for unhealthy vs healthy soils based on literature data

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Table 2 (continued)

Framework	Purpose	Key indicators	Score calculation
SQIw (Vasu et al., 2024)	Evaluate soil quality under different soil types and regions, with a focus on soil health and crop productivity	Chemical, physical and biological measures, as well as plant and animal health indicators	Expert opinions and PCA are combined for indicator selection, scores are given based on significant correlation coefficients, which are normalized and weighted into a single score
Gilarte et al. (current study)	Quantify damage to specific soil related functions and services as areas of protection.	Middle and endpoint indicators to be selected for each outlined function across the impact pathway	LCA based modelling via literature specified equations for fate, concentration and exposure of different stressors linked to biodiversity loss and the resulting damage to soil functions and services

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Damage pathways in current soil health frameworks

A total of 23 different approaches for soil health assessment were identified in our literature search (e.g., Guo, 2021; Chang et al., 2022; Wade et al., 2022). They are shown in chronological order in Table 2. Details describing each framework can be found in the SI (see Section S2 for details).

The following main observations can be made: (1) Impact pathway mechanisms are generally not considered in the frameworks. This is not necessarily a limitation and does not disqualify any of the proposed approaches. It may, however, jeopardize the understanding of how different soil stressors contribute to soil health damage. (2) Current soil health frameworks vary in their assessed functions, ranging from zero to several, with a focus on primary production, nutrient and carbon cycling.

Regarding indicator use and selection, (3) the current frameworks vary in number and characteristics of indicators; commonly used metrics include physiochemical soil parameters such as soil pH, organic carbon content, bulk density, aggregate stability, or nutrient levels (e.g., phosphorus, potassium), as well as indicators of biological activity in soils. Some frameworks do consider specific functions like soil organic carbon dynamics, as well as ecotoxicological and human health parameters. Examples include the Soil Carbon Index (Zobeck et al., 2008) and ERICA (Boriani et al., 2010). (4) The relationship between each indicator and soil health is usually assessed via the use of scoring curves, establishing the correlation between each indicator and soil health status. The predominant approaches to a scoring system involve using mathematical ordination methods, such as principal component analysis (PCA) for indicator selection and weighting, as well as context-specific selection of relevant soil properties into specific indicators (e.g. stakeholder opinions, literature reviews). The various scores associated with each indicator are then compiled to create a composite score. Many of the frameworks covered also use expert opinion when considering the weighting of different indicators (see details in Table 2).

Concerning their application, (5) the dominant uses of current soil health frameworks are for monitoring soil health changes due to land use and management practices, whereas applications for pollution risk assessment or crop management recommendations are less frequent. (6) Soil biological activity and biodiversity indicators are being progressively included into more recent developments (e.g., SMI, EUSO, SQIw). However, biodiversity measurements are yet to be incorporated in a quantifiable way which translates damages resulting from species loss to the subsequent losses to soil functions and services.

3.2. Damage pathways in current environmental impact assessment practice

Fig. 1 provides an overview of the main impact mechanisms linking soil stressors to species biodiversity loss, based on our literature review. The left panel (impact pathway) showcases the different stressors to soil health. Below, we discuss these mechanisms in detail for each stressor category.

Overall, our review reveals that life cycle assessment practices differ

fundamentally from existing soil health frameworks, suggesting opportunities for learning from one another. Impact assessment approaches are generally consistent and rigorous in modeling the effects of soil stressors, avoiding overlaps and expressing damage at the species biodiversity level. However, they do not connect species loss to the loss of soil functions and ecosystem services, which is a key objective of soil health assessment (Li et al., 2023).

Mechanistic insights from impact assessment methods, particularly how soil stressors influence biodiversity and indicators of species loss, could on the other hand inspire soil health assessments, which typically rely heavily on physicochemical indicators such as soil pH. Conversely, impact assessment methods could benefit from soil health frameworks by incorporating mechanisms beyond biodiversity, such as threats to biological functions, as seen in the EUSO framework (Panagos et al., 2024).

3.2.1. Organic compounds and metals

The impact pathway for ecotoxicity of organic chemicals and metallic compounds (including metals and metalloids) consists of three major components: environmental fate, ecosystem exposure and ecotoxicological effects (Fantke et al., 2021; Owsianiak et al., 2023). The environmental fate includes the distribution of chemicals between environmental compartments (i.e. multimedia transfer) as controlled by fate active processes within each compartment, like degradation, aging and weathering (for metals) and transport processes including runoff from soil to freshwater, outflow from freshwater to coastal seawater, or leaching to groundwater. The ecosystem exposure determines which fraction of a chemical in a given soil compartment is actually available to organisms for uptake and bioaccumulation. Soil organisms are mainly exposed via the water phase, but also through the soil matrix and gas phase (e.g. Gall et al., 2015). Thus, the exposure is mainly controlled by distribution of a chemical between these phases in soils.

For most cationic metals, speciation within the liquid phase is important, as they contain bioavailable free ions and inorganic complexes (Gandhi et al., 2010). Speciation within the solid phase (e.g. in soil) is also a relevant mechanism influencing exposure for metals (Owsianiak et al., 2013, 2015; Sydow et al., 2020). The ecotoxicological effect factor quantifies the ecotoxicological impact on species loss due to exposure to the bioavailable mass of a substance. It is derived from species sensitivity distribution curves (Fantke et al., 2018; Posthuma et al., 2019). Resulting concentration–response functions are combined with a severity factor to translate organism effects to potentially disappeared fractions of species (Fantke et al., 2018).

Inorganic substances other than metals, including those resulting from soil transformations of organic and metallic compounds, are also slowly being integrated into ecotoxicity impacts (Kirchhübel and Fantke, 2019). Their toxicity is highly dependent upon soil kinetics and environmental factors, with further steps required for their full incorporation into impact categories (e.g., Owsianiak et al., 2023).

3.2.2. Plastics

Plastics are relatively novel substances which follow a similar ecotoxicity pathway to chemicals, encompassing environmental fate, ecosystem exposure, and ecotoxicological effects. However, plastics are additionally linked to physical impacts (e.g. smothering), and thus

Fig. 1. Proposed damage pathways from anthropogenic stressors resulting in environmental interactions to affected soil functions and related ecosystem services, consistent with life cycle impact assessment source-to-damage modelling principles.

behave as a “diverse contaminant suite” (Rochman et al., 2019; Li et al., 2023, 2024; Guruge et al., 2024). The environmental fate of plastics is influenced by fragmentation (size change) and degradation (mineralization), which are affected by both external conditions and internal properties (Galafton et al., 2025). Additionally, transport processes involving plastics of various densities and sizes include runoff to freshwater, outflow to seawater, deposition and resuspension in the air, and leaching to groundwater (Rochman et al., 2019; Woods et al., 2021; Li et al., 2023). Unlike chemicals, which rely on water solubility for ecosystem exposure via passive uptake, the presence of plastic particles (e.g., microplastics) ensure exposure through physical contact too, regardless of their phase distribution (Corella-Puertas et al., 2023; Li et al., 2023, 2024).

The ecological impacts of plastics are extensive, encompassing direct physical effects from “particles” and broader effects associated with their status as a “diverse contaminant suite”. This latter category includes interactions from chemical leachates and constituents of the plastisphere (Guruge et al., 2024; Rillig et al., 2024). The plastic degradation process produces GHG emissions and is linked to other impact pathways (Galafton et al., 2025).

Chemical leachates from plastics can be quantified via chemical and metal impact pathways (Brander et al., 2024; Suh et al., 2025; Galafton et al., 2025). In line with chemicals, ecotoxicological effect factors for plastics are also defined, and derived using species sensitivity distribution curves. Both physical and ecotoxicological effects of plastics should

be fully integrated into damage models, including lesser reported effects like the transportation of pathogens and facilitating the development and spread of antimicrobial resistance via plastic particles (Maga et al., 2022; Guruge et al., 2024).

3.2.3. Climate forcers

Climate forcers, like greenhouse gases (GHG), non-methane volatile organic compounds, halocarbons, or aerosols (e.g. black carbon) stemming from airborne emissions, undergo mixing in the atmosphere and fate processes like degradation (e.g., CO, through reactions with hydroxyl radicals) or uptake into ocean (CO₂). Their presence in the atmosphere increases radiative forcing (i.e., net solar energy trapped in the atmosphere), which results in subsequent changes (globally an increase) in atmospheric temperature. This temperature change results in loss of habitats, causing organisms to respond by trying to find new suitable habitats, or to modify their behaviours and activities (Urban, 2015; Chang et al., 2019). This may lead to increased risk of local or global species extinction (Verones et al., 2022). Response of organisms to loss of habitat varies geographically as it depends on factors like endemism, type of taxon, or level of dispersal of the species (Urban, 2015; Keck et al., 2025).

Positive feedback loops are particularly relevant to consider in the case of climate change. Increase in atmospheric temperature results in crossing of climate tipping points, like collapse of ice sheets, thawing of permafrost, or shutdown of ocean–atmosphere circulations (Lenton

et al., 2023). Additionally, climate impacts can worsen the effects of intensive agriculture (Yang et al., 2024). Crossing of a tipping point leads to an additional increase in the temperature (adding on top of the increase from background emissions), further contributing to the local (or global) loss of species (Fabbri et al., 2021). For some of the tipping points (e.g., for forest dieback), direct effects of crossing some tipping points on species loss may also be a relevant impact mechanism.

3.2.4. Nutrients and acidifying substances

The impact pathway for nutrients in LCIA methodology is addressed within the context of excess nutrients, which are predominantly associated with marine and freshwater eutrophication and, to a lesser extent, terrestrial acidification (Huijbregts et al., 2017; Gade et al., 2021). This connection to acidification may be linked to specific phases of nutrient cycles involving nitrogen and sulphur oxides (Roem and Berendse, 2000; Azevedo et al., 2013). Freshwater and marine eutrophication are primarily driven by excess amounts of the vital nutrients phosphorus and nitrogen, respectively. In soils, nitrogen is an essential macronutrient, but excess can cause eutrophication (Smith et al., 1999).

The specific nutrients contributing to soil eutrophication and acidification can vary spatially and temporally (Gade et al., 2021). To align the nutrient impact pathway with frameworks used for other stressors, the fate processes encompass the movement of nutrients both within terrestrial systems and between compartments such as freshwater, atmospheric, and marine environments. Additionally, these processes involve biogeochemical transformations including nitrification, denitrification, and phosphorus sorption or release, all of which are influenced by spatial and temporal factors, particularly in soil contexts. The environmental exposure in the context of eutrophication is complex, as nutrients do not cause direct impacts but rather secondary effects via transformations into different substances.

For terrestrial eutrophication, critical thresholds of soil solution ammonium or nitrate concentrations below which no detectable ecosystem changes occur have been proposed as potential indicators (Smith et al., 1999). This approach is similar to the case for marine ecosystems, where the lowest observed effect concentration (LOEC) is estimated based on sensitivity to hypoxia (Cosme and Hauschild, 2016). However, current LCIA methods rarely explicitly address terrestrial eutrophication due to several challenges, such as high geographic variability, and overlap with other stressor categories like acidification and land use change (Bulle et al., 2019; Conci et al., 2022). These indicators collectively impact ecosystem quality and are linked to damage measures which are expressed in a common unit of potentially disappeared fraction of species (PDF.m².yr) in terrestrial environments (Frischknecht et al., 2018; Verones et al., 2022).

In the case of terrestrial acidification, there is an increase in soil proton concentration (i.e., a reduction in pH) (e.g., Prosser, 2011; Ma et al., 2021). To quantify this impact, a sensitivity factor (SF) or response factor (RF) mathematically equivalent to an exposure factor (XF) is used to represent changes in the buffering capacity of soil systems (Lebrun et al., 2025).

3.2.5. Land use and land use change

Land use and land use change are stressors that alter the physical, chemical, and biological properties of soil through processes like erosion, compaction, and sealing from infrastructure (Milà i Canals et al., 2007; Montanarella et al., 2016; Tobias et al., 2018). In LCIA, the primary impact pathway for land use is conceptualized through land occupation and land transformation (Bulle et al., 2019; Inaba and Itsubo, 2018; Koellner et al., 2013), corresponding to the terms “land use” and “land-use change” commonly used outside the LCA community (Brandão, et al., 2021).

Although land use can cause the accumulation or depletion of soil nutrients and contaminants potentially leading to eutrophication, acidification, or toxicity, these impacts are considered separate impact categories in line with LCIA methodology, which advocates for

complementarity and avoidance of double counting (e.g., Gebara et al., 2024; see these impact categories described above). The impact pathway for land use is described by processes that affect soil properties, leading to modifications in soil characteristics and, ultimately, the disruption of key soil functions. The common impact pathways include changes in soil moisture, structural stability, nutrient availability, and soil organic carbon (SOC), among others (e.g., Verheijen et al., 2009; Smith et al., 2015). For example, as an impact pathway, SOC plays a key role in nutrient cycling, carbon transformations, and the maintenance of soil structure (Lehmann and Kleber, 2015). Soil erosion is an exceptional case where soil loss occurs, i.e. loss of the soil itself (Verheijen et al., 2009).

Land use effects are linked to relative species richness, which is defined as the ratio of species richness under a specific land use type to that of a reference natural ecosystem, as is commonly used in LCIA to quantify ecosystem quality damage due to land use impacts (De Baan et al., 2013). The land use effect factors are estimated based on the loss in relative species richness (RSR) compared to a reference land use, multiplied by the area and duration of land occupation or transformation.

3.3. Damage to soil functions and related ecosystem services

A summary of our findings, illustrating the link between soil functions and the resulting ecosystem services through specific organisms and the processes they contribute to in soils, is presented in Table 3. Soil functions and resulting services vary greatly in their underlying processes and organisms responsible for these. For instance, some functions are underpinned by a large number of processes and organisms (habitat for biodiversity, population regulation), while others, like biomass production, have discrete functional groups directly responsible for their performance (i.e., autotrophs). Similarly, soil functions which are highly dependent upon the physical medium, or which occur at higher geological time scales, are less susceptible (but still modified by, to a lesser extent) to biodiversity changes (e.g., archive of information). Likewise, several functions can interact and/or influence a given service. These outlined variations can aid in the development of future modeling steps.

We argue that the strength of impact assessment can be leveraged to develop a comprehensive damage pathway. In our Glossary, we define soil related ecosystem services as the human benefits resulting from soil functions (Table 1). This definition aligns with LCA methods, allowing the streamlining of our proposed damage pathway as a cause-and-effect chain. This pathway combines the impact routes from soil stressors to biodiversity loss (Fig. 1, left panel) with a systemic understanding of damage mechanisms affecting soil functions and services (Table 3). To achieve this, we translated the information in Table 3 into a structured damage pathway that links species biodiversity loss (that is, the current endpoint in impact assessment) with the loss of associated soil functions and ecosystem services. This involved detailing biodiversity loss into the decline of key organisms and connecting these organisms to the soil functions and services they influence. The resulting representation highlights which organisms are particularly critical for delivering one or more soil ecosystem services. Fig. 1 (right panel) presents this part of the full damage pathway. These two pathways effectively connect via zooming into the different functional roles of soil organisms, highlighted here as losses to functional diversity (see “damage to species” in Fig. 1).

3.4. Steps toward operationalization in life cycle assessment

3.4.1. Defining the area of protection

The area of protection (AoP) in environmental sustainability is defined as “the entity that we want to protect” (Finnveden et al., 2009). Considering each ecosystem service as a separate AoP would align with the definition of soil health, since soil health is essentially the capacity to provide ecosystem services that support “human lives on Earth.” If each

ecosystem service is treated as a separate area of protection, then losses of soil functions would correspond to damage categories. This approach would be analogous to existing sustainability assessment frameworks, which define ecosystem quality, human health, and natural resources as areas of protection and use Disability-Adjusted Life Years (DALYs), Potentially Disappeared Fraction (PDF) of species over area and time, and resource depletion or dissipation as damage categories.

Defining area(s) of protection is not only a conceptual exercise; it is often overlooked leading to potential disagreements about which sustainability objectives (quantifiable limits) and which indicators are appropriate. For example, development goals of the EU Soil Mission, like reducing soil erosion or carbon regulation, can be considered as separate areas of protection, potentially requiring different sets of indicators than those which focus on other soil functions and ecosystem services (Panagos et al., 2022; Veerman, 2023).

3.4.2. Selection and modelling of soil health indicators

Inspired by the literature on indicator selection for environmental sustainability assessment (Gebara et al., 2024), we suggest basing indicator selection on the following principles. First, the indicator must be related to the sustainability objective, i.e., in this case relevant for the given soil function or ecosystem service offered by the soil. Second, the indicator should be based on a mechanistic understanding of the underlying processes from emissions, or resource use, to the resulting ecosystem damage. The damage pathways presented in Fig. 1 must be consulted to make this meaningful. Indicators can then be chosen at any point in the impact pathway. Indicators positioned early offer the advantage of being more readily available or easier to quantify. Damage

indicators positioned later in the impact pathway might require significant modelling efforts, but may be easier to interpret, hence facilitating the comparison of the different stressors contributing to ecosystem damage. Third, indicators should be mutually exclusive (i.e., not overlapping with other indicators on the impact pathway) and collectively exhaustive (covering all relevant aspects of the sustainability objective).

At this stage, we do not suggest which specific indicator(s) should be used, as this is beyond the scope of our review. We however propose adhering to the aforementioned principles when selecting appropriate metrics. Irrespective of which indicators are chosen, there might be a need to aggregate losses of different functions (or losses of different services) into a single score representing the loss of soil health to facilitate interpretation in a decision support context. This can also present a challenge. One approach is to implement weighting schemes, which would allow aggregating individual indicator scores based on weight (e.g., do Carmo et al., 2017; Paracchini et al., 2008). An alternative approach could be to express potential loss of functions or services in monetary terms to enable aggregation based on a common monetary metric (Baveye et al., 2016; Mikhailova et al., 2020).

3.4.3. Dealing with positive and negative impacts

Soil health assessments integrating soil functions and ecosystem services might result in situations where certain interventions (e.g., increase in soil organic carbon through the addition of soil bio-improvers, with potential co-contaminants like excess nutrients or metals) may lead to an increase in the capability of a soil to support human lives (via enhancing its capacity to provide an ecosystem service) at the expense of other functions and related services (e.g., increasing toxic pressure in the

Table 3

Main soil associated functions and services with important underlying processes and examples of the key soil organisms involved.

Soil functions	Key organisms (examples)	Underlying processes	Brief definition	Resulting ecosystem service (s)
Archive of information	Some chemotrophs, extinct organisms necromass	Strata deposition, burial, fossilization and precipitation over geological timescales	Geological strata deposition and preservation	Source of knowledge (archaeological, paleontological, geological, etc.)
Biomass Production	Autotrophs (e.g. crop species like edible grains and legumes), consumers (livestock, game), Basidiomycota (edible mushrooms), and growth promoting bacteria (e.g. <i>Streptomyces griseoviridis</i>).	Photosynthesis, grazing, predation.	Energy transformation into organic matter.	Food and fibre provision.
Carbon cycling	Autotrophs, heterotrophs, mycorrhizae (e.g. <i>Rhizopogon luteolus</i>)	Photosynthesis, respiration, root proliferation and symbiosis, litter and necromass accumulation, decomposition	Biogeochemical transformations of carbon compounds for their eventual reuse or dissipation	Carbon sequestration and microclimate regulation
Genetic and molecular diversity	Vascular plants, fungi (e.g. <i>Penicillium chrysogenum</i>), some microbes, yeasts	Immunity, allelopathy, chemical defences, metabolic processes	Genetic diversity or complexity of a community	Provision of varieties, cultivars, resistance genes, pharmaceuticals
Nutrient cycling	Saprotrophs, chemotrophs, root symbionts (e.g. <i>Rhizobium leguminosarum</i>), invertebrates (e.g. detritivores)	Decomposition, OM breakdown, biogeochemical transformations (e.g. biological N fixation)	Biogeochemical transformations of macro and micronutrients for their eventual reuse or dissipation	Soil fertility
Habitat for biodiversity	r-strategists, seeds, spores, ground nesting pollinators (e.g. <i>Dasyptoda maura</i>)	Dispersion, phoresis, colonization, pollination, facilitation	Stable surface for organisms to colonise and inhabit	Biodiversity provision
Physical platform	Human beings (<i>Homo sapiens</i>)	Soil formation and erosion, human activities	Stable surface for humans to inhabit	Space for human activities and infrastructures
Pollutant degradation	Bacteria (e.g. <i>Pseudomonas fluorescens</i>), some vascular plants (e.g. <i>Helianthus anuum</i>)	Phytoremediation, microbial degradation and depolymerization, chelation	Breakdown of contaminants into less harmful substances	Bioremediation
Population regulation	Herbivores, predators, parasites, parasitoids and pathogens (e.g. <i>Steinernema feltiae</i>)	Grazing, predation, parasitism, competition, disturbance	Populational dynamics keeping ecosystems below their carrying capacity	Disease, pest and invasive species control
Raw materials production	Chemotrophic microorganisms (e.g. <i>Nitrobacter</i> sp.)	Mineralization, sedimentation, precipitation, weathering	Deposition of minerals and other useful inorganic materials	Provision of material goods
Soil formation	Vascular plants, bryophytes, microorganisms (e.g. <i>Geobacter</i> sp.), invertebrates (e.g. earthworms like <i>Eisenia fetida</i>)	Rock weathering, bioturbation, litter and necromass accumulation, organic matter (OM) humification	Biogeochemical transformation of parent material into soil	Erosion control
Water regulation	Vascular plants (e.g. native grasses)	Filtering, percolation, infiltration, storage and redistribution of water	The infiltration, storage and redistribution of water in soils	Flood and storm control, underground water provision

long-term). Dealing with positive and negative effects is therefore necessary, as it is evident that the enhancement of certain, profitable soil functions often comes at the expense of reducing others (e.g., Valujeva et al., 2016). This trade-off must be considered in the evaluation of soil health scores and potential weighting of underlying soil function or ecosystem service impacts (Tamburini et al., 2016; Gao et al., 2024). This aspect is particularly relevant to assess soil recovery, such as the contribution to soil health of different bio-improvers, cover crops, and other management strategies which result in “positive” effects (Jiang et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2023).

3.4.4. Elucidating the role of “ecosystem engineers”

More research is needed to quantify the extent to which specific organisms contribute to a given function under a variety of conditions (Ferris and Tuomisto, 2015; Römbke et al., 2018). An important area for further research is the distinction of key species, also known as ecosystem engineers, and the role of intra-functional species redundancy. Ecology recognises the important role of ecosystem engineers, which greatly contribute to the delivery of one or more functions and services (Lavelle et al., 2016). Part of a realistic soil health assessment should place such species in high regard. However, different species will contribute to a given function to varying degrees depending upon favourable niche conditions on site (e.g. Qin et al., 2022). Additionally, intra-functional diversity can provide much buoyancy to navigate stressors via the role of species redundancy, providing resistance and resilience (Bennett et al., 2020; Girvan et al., 2005). As a result, the concept of ecosystem engineering species has been expanded to the community level (Mouquet et al., 2013).

Recent analyses have highlighted that ecosystem engineers disproportionately contribute to ecosystem processes across multiple ecological niche dimensions (e.g. Byers, 2022; Losapio et al., 2024). Identifying these, their contributions and optimal conditions is hence a necessary step towards integrating the role of biodiversity into soil health assessment frameworks. We have included a few general examples to illustrate our flow diagram (e.g. mycorrhiza, pollinating insects, see Fig. 1, Table 3), but these are by no means exhaustive. We expect these species to highly contribute to a given function and service, making them a good candidate for quantitative modelling of our proposed flow diagram as a next step.

4. Conclusions

We showed that none of the existing soil health assessment frameworks are currently able to systematically take soil stressor emissions or land use as a starting point for soil health assessment and therefore cannot yet be linked to quantitative assessment tools. Furthermore, with the exception of EUSO, damages to soil functions and ecosystem services are generally not considered in current soil health assessments. These limitations are not necessarily problematic, as different frameworks have different applications and may well serve their intended purposes, which was not evaluated in this review. However, this highlights a paradox in the current understanding of soil health, which is often approximated by parameters that, although useful, do not allow to fully quantify damage to soil health. Finally, we showed that existing impact assessment approaches, such as life cycle impact assessment, commonly applied in quantitative sustainability assessments using tools like LCA, also do not consider damages to soil health, understood as “the capability of a soil to maintain its functions for the support of life on Earth, including human lives” (Karlen et al., 2019).

We therefore propose linking the existing impact assessment tools, which offer a systematic understanding of impact and damage mechanisms from stressors to species biodiversity loss, with a systematic understanding of damage pathways from this biodiversity loss to the loss of soil functions and resulting ecosystem services as presented in the current review. Our full damage pathway should be seen as the first necessary step toward including soil health in quantitative sustainability

assessment.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Patricia Gilarte: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation. **Amila Abeynayaka:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Peter Fantke:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Mikołaj Owsianiak:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2026.117776>.

Data availability

This review article does not include original data. All the information presented is derived from previously published studies, which are cited in the manuscript. No new datasets were generated or analysed during the current study.

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